

INFLUENCE OF SURFACE TREATMENTS ON HYDROPHILITY OF NATURAL FIBERS

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SUMMARY: Several researches related to the use of natural fibers in polymeric matrix composites have been developed. The presence of –OH groups in some of their chemical components generate an important hydrophilic tendency that produces adhesion lacks with hydrophobic polymeric matrices. In this work different natural fibers have been modified by silanization, esterification and mercerization processes. The natural fibers analyzed are fique, sisal and banana fibers extracted from stem of plants. To evaluate the changes introduced by treatments on chemical structure of fibers, FTIR spectrophotometry has been employed. The evaluation of advancing dynamic contact angles and the determination of total surface free energy by using the Owens-Wendt method indicate that the treatments allow to reduce the hydrophilic tendency of natural fibers by alterations on the physico-chemical characteristics of the fiber. This reduction is confirmed with the reduction of moisture sorption, analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis.

KEYWORDS: Natural fibers, fiber treatments, hydrophilic tendency, contact angle, chemical composition.

INTRODUCTION

Several researches related to the use of natural fibers in polymeric matrix composites have been developed. As reinforcement, natural fibers present different advantages as low density, medium stiffness, appropriate thermal resistance to processing conditions, high disposability and renovability and low abrasion [1-3]. The introduction of natural fibers into composites increases the stiffness but maintaining the low density of the neat matrix.

The main compounds present in the chemical composition of natural fibers correspond to cellulose, lignin and hemicellulose. These structures contain –OH groups, thus leading to the strong hydrophilic

tendency of natural fibers. This characteristic generally leads to problems of adhesion with polymeric matrices, especially due to their strong hydrophobic behavior. Therefore, the mechanical behavior and moisture absorption resistance of their composites appears to be poor.

For enhancement of natural fiber/polymer adhesion, different alternatives such as fiber modification, matrix modification or coupling agent addition exist. Fiber modification may cause alterations on the physical and chemical characteristics of the fibers. It can also introduce alterations on the surface behavior. In this study, the reduction of the hydrophilic tendency of different natural fibers has been evaluated as a function of different chemical treatments. The natural fibers analyzed have been: sisal, fique fibers and banana fibers. Surface fiber treatments such as mercerization, γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy-silane (GLYMO) and esterification with maleic anhydride (MA) have been employed.

Fourier transformation infrared spectrophotometry (FTIR) has been employed for following the fiber changes after treatments. The dynamic contact angles for each type of fibers have been measured by using the Owens-Wendt method to determine the variations of the surface free energy. Additionally, TGA analysis and moisture sorption tests have also been performed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: The fique fibers were kindly provided by Compañía de Empaques S.A. (Medellin/Colombia), the sisal fibers were kindly supplied by Celesa (Spain) and the banana fibers were extracted in the Mechanical Laboratories of UPB (Medellín/Colombia) of stems of *Valery* specie from Urabá region (Colombia). The chemical agents used are maleic anhydride (CEPSA), and γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy-silane (GLYMO), kindly supplied by Degussa - Hüls.

Fiber Surface Modification: Previous to the treatments, all fibers were dried at $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. For mercerization treatment (M), a 20 wt% sodium hydroxide solution was used during one hour. The fibers were repeatedly washed with distilled water with a few drops of acetic acid, hereafter washing with distilled water until neutral pH. The fibers were dried for 24 h at $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

For esterification treatment with maleic anhydride (MA), fique fibers were immersed in a solution with acetone as solvent. The treatment was carried out for 25 h at $55 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. After the treatment, the fibers were washed with acetone and distilled water to remove all unreacted components and oven dried at $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. This reaction was evaluated at different process times, between 1 - 25 hours. For silane treatment, the fibers were immersed in silane methanol solution for 1 ½ h. Then, the fibers were dried at $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h.

Test Methods: FTIR infrared spectroscopy, Perkin Elmer PC1600, was employed for analyzing the variations on fiber chemical composition after treatments. The spectra were taken at a spectra resolution of 4 cm^{-1} with twenty scans for each specimen.

The dynamical contact angle were measured a Krüss K14 dynamic contact angle analyzer using the

Wilhelmy plate technique [4]. In this method, single fibers are dipped into the probe liquids up to a depth of 2 mm with a speed of $50 \mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. During the test, it is possible to obtain the advancing and retreating angles. The advancing angle has been employed due to its reproducibility. The probe liquids used by contact angle determination were water, ethyleneglycol and α -bromonaphthalene at 24°C . The surface energy parameter of probe liquids employed are registered in table 1. Ten single fibers were investigated for each treatment and type of fibers. The surface free energy was calculating using the Owens-Wendt method [4]. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of untreated and treated fibers was carried out in helium atmosphere at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, using a thermoanalyser, Setaram 92 - 12.

Table 1. Surface parameters of probe liquids.

Liquid	Polar component (mJ/m^2)	Total free energy surface (mJ/m^2)
Water	50.8	72.4
Ethyleneglycol	21.3	47.0
α -Bromonaphthalene	---	44.4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Infrared spectroscopy study

FTIR spectrophotometry is an appropriate technology to establish the variations introduced by the different treatments on chemical structure of natural fibers. FTIR spectra for untreated and treated fique fibers are registered in figures 1 and 2. The spectra for other fibers as banana and sisal are comparable with those for fique fibers, though they present slight shifts in position of some peaks respect to fique fiber spectra. The mainly chemical components of these natural fibers are: cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Some characteristics bands observed in figure 1 are the vibration at 2863 cm^{-1} of $-\text{OCH}_3$ stretching of lignin, 1737 cm^{-1} that corresponds to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bonds associated with hemicellulose and lignin, 1182 cm^{-1} of $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ bond of glucose ring of cellulose or 900 cm^{-1} related to glucose ring stretching, The most significant effects introduced by mercerization are associated with the attenuation of 1743 cm^{-1} vibration that corresponds to the reduction of presence of hemicellulose, and the attenuation of 1500 cm^{-1} and 1268 cm^{-1} related with the aromatic skeletal of lignin [5]. These changes have also been observed in other studies [4, 6]. Respect to silane treatments, the mainly variations are observed nearly 810 cm^{-1} and between $1100\text{-}1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These vibrations are associated with $\text{Si}-\text{C}$ bonds and $\text{Si}-\text{OH}$, respectively. The presence of these vibrations indicates the effectiveness of this treatment process. For the esterification process, the treated fibers present a vibration at 1737 cm^{-1} associated with the vibration characteristic of a new carbonyl group formed

during the esterification reaction between –OH groups of fiber with maleic anhydride.

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of untreated (----), mercerized (ΓΓ), and silanized fique fibers (| |)

Figure 2. FTIR spectra of esterified (| |) and mercerized fique fibers (---)

Advancing contact angles and Surface free energy

To analyze the hydrophilic behavior of treated and untreated natural fibers, the contact angle technique has been used. The surface parameter of probe liquids must be different to evaluate the polar and dispersive components of the total free surface energy of fibers by Owens-Wendt method. Owens-Wendt developed a semiempirical equation, which is referred as a geometric mean:

$$\sigma_{sL} = \sigma_s + \sigma_L - 2 * ((\sigma_s^d * \sigma_L^d)^{0.5} + (\sigma_s^p * \sigma_L^p)^{0.5})$$

with: σ_s , fiber - liquid interfacial surface free energy, σ_L , surface free energy for the probe liquid, each parameter containing dispersive (d) and polar (p) components [4].

Figures 3-4 and Tables 2-3 show the dynamic contact angles and surface free energies of different natural fibers. The different untreated fibers present comparable contact angles with each probe liquid. It indicates that these natural fibers present a comparable surface distribution of their polar and dispersive components. The effect introduced by each surface treatment could be reproducible in other fibers with similar characteristics. The contact angles observed with water and α -bromonaphthalene indicate that these fibers have both polar and dispersive components.

Figure 3. Advancing contact angle for treated

Figure 4. Surface free energy for untreated

However, the highest contact angles obtained with ethyleneglycol ratifies the strong polar tendency of surface of the natural fibers studied. The wettability analysis by Owens – Wendt method confirms this observation, since the polar component is nearly to 50% total surface free energy for all natural fibers analyzed. This behavior is associated with the –OH groups presence in chemical structures such as cellulose, and it has an important vibration on IR spectra around of 3400 cm^{-1} .

Table 2. Advancing contact angles for banana fibers

Type of treatment	W (°)	EG (°)	α -B (°)
Untreated	45.3	46.1	55.7
Silanized	70.6	33.3	44.5
Mercerized	63.9	37.1	50.8

W: Water; EG:, Ethyleneglycoand; α -B: α -bromonaphthalene.

Table 3. Surface parameters for banana fibers

Type of treatment	Polar component (mJ/m ²)	Total free energy surface (mJ/m ²)
Untreated	24.3	47.3

Silanized	10.3	38.8
Mercerized	16.2	40.3

The contact angles in water of treated fibers increase respect to the values of untreated fibers, while they decrease with ethyleneglycol. In the same way, the polar component of surface free energy of treated fibers decrease, with slight variations on the total surface free energy. These variations reflect the changes in surface characteristics of fibers introduced by each treatment. In the case of mercerization process, this changes are associated with the increment on the fiber roughness and the reduction of chemical structures, as shown above. For esterification treatment, the reduction on hydrophilic tendency is related to the reaction of –OH groups, while for silanized fibers the reduction could be related with the presence of new chemical interactions.

In general, the polar component of mercerized fibers is higher than that for the other treated fibers. This behavior can be associated with higher sorption of the probe liquid due to the roughness of fiber [7], which can affect the determination of contact angle.

The variations observed on surface free energy for untreated and treated natural fibers are comparable with values reported by others authors [7] using other methods of analysis such as inverse gas chromatography (IGC) with naturals fibers as jute.

Thermal Analysis

The thermal analysis by dynamical assay provides information about the regions of loss weight of fibers. Figures 5 and 6 present the TGA analysis of different untreated and treated fibers. The natural fibers present two mainly weigh loss regions: between 50-125°C and 210-450°C. The first decomposition region is associated with moisture sorption. These natural fibers can gain moisture in amounts between 4.5 and 7 wt% . However, the treated fibers present an important reduction of these values, see table 4. This behavior is related with the reduction on hydrophilic tendency of fibers.

Table 4. Weight loss in THE first decomposition region for different fibers

<i>Banana fiber</i>		<i>Fique fiber</i>	
	Weight loss (%)		Weight loss (%)
Untreated	5.47	Untreated	4.60
Silanized	2.00	Silanized	1.70
Mercerized	2.92	Mercerized	3.03

Figure 5. Thermogravimetical analysis of untreated (--) and treated fique fibers (▲)

Figure 6. Thermogravimetical analysis of untreated (--) and treated sisal fibers (▲) in first weight decomposition region

The highest reduction of moisture sorption for all natural fibers studied has been obtained with silanization treatment. These results are in agreement with previous work [4].

In the second decomposition region, it is possible to observe that the mainly decomposition process occurs in the range between 300-400°C, where cellulose decomposition takes place.

When analyzing the maximal decomposition temperature of untreated fibers respect to treated ones, see table 5, the results indicate that treated fibers are more stable than untreated fibers. This thermal stability can be related to the presence of new groups on fiber surface, specially by the effect of bonds such as Si-C or Si-OH. The reduction of xylans, component of hemicellulose, in the chemical composition of mercerized fibers, contribute to increase the thermal stability, since this structure present the lower thermal resistance than that cellulose. According with this the hemicellulose represents the thermally most unstable natural fiber component. The removal of hemicellulose can leave fiber stability during melt processsing and reduces the formation of volatile degradation products [8].

According with table 5, fique fibers present a higher thermal stability than that the other natural fibers analyzed. The thermal stability of the analyzed fibers suggests that they can be processed using conventional technologies employed for thermoplastic or thermosetting materials.

Table 5. Maximal decomposition temperatures in THE second region

Type of treatment	Maximal decomposition
<i>Banana fiber</i>	
Untreated	353
Silanized	392
Mercerized	370
<i>Fique fiber</i>	
Untreated	365
Silanized	395
Mercerized	385
<i>Sisal fiber</i>	
Untreated	355
Silanized	390
Mercerized	355

CONCLUSIONS

Because the hydrophilic tendency of natural fibers, it is necessary to employ surface treatments for their compatibilization with hydrophobic matrices. This study has shown that surface treatments affect the chemical structure and the surface and thermal behavior of fibers. According with the results obtained in this study, it is possible to conclude that:

- All natural fibers employed have an important polar component, associated with the presence of –OH groups present in their chemical components. The strong hydrophilic tendency is responsible of the moisture sorption of fibers.
- Results of surface free energy show that with silanization fibers present a lower polar component than for mercerization.
- Silanization and mercerization treatments allow to reduce the polar component by combination of different effects as introduction of new bonds or reduction of chemical components, and also alteration on physical structure of fibers.
- Surface treatments increase the thermal stability of natural fibers.

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